

QUALITY OF PEDAGOGIC STRATEGIES IN TEACHING MULTIGRADE CLASSES IN THE DIVISION OF QUEZON

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Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in the Division of Quezon

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Abstract

The study focused on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in the Division of Quezon. The study applied descriptive survey method for the study with the Questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. A total of 81 respondents participated in the study. Statistical tools were utilized such as frequency count, mean scores, Mann Whitney U-Test and Kruskal Wallis H-Test. The study revealed that a typical respondent comprised of age 21 to 30 years old, female-dominated, married individuals, with Master's Units, were in Teacher I position, and served the school for 1 to 5 years. Also, the study concluded that quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes was given a very good rating in the Division of Quezon. When it comes to Peer Teaching or Tutoring, it showed that the administrators and teachers apply differentiated learning instruction to ensure learning will take place in school. According to Competency-based Learning, it stated that competency-based education is applied by the Multigrade teachers following the K-12 Curriculum and MELCs based competencies. In terms of Direct Instruction, it elicited that multigrade Instruction is evaluated or assessed through formative and summative assessments for the period. In addition, the study concluded that the respondents often encountered the problems in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. This showed that the students lack gadgets to be used for internet classes for differentiated learning approach. Next item elicited that there are problems with the internet connectivity for differentiated approach. This was followed by the statement which said that the location of Multigrade schools are the reasons why facilities and other construction are not readily available. And, there is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to profile except for Teacher's Rank on Peer Teaching or Tutoring which is statistically significant on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to profile.

Keywords: *competency-based education, differentiated instruction, multigrade classes, peer teaching, pedagogic strategies*

Introduction

Based on the global perspective of multi-grade teaching, several literatures refer to this as "multi-level, multiple class, composite class, vertical group, family class, and in the case of open teacher school, and unitary school. In this regard, multi-grade teaching is defined as the teaching of learners with varied ages, grades, and abilities in the group. Here, the school requires children from more than one grade to be taught together and given several learning activities for an appropriate level for each grade with independent benefit from the competencies needed to be acquired (Sampson & Condy, 2016).

Referring to old pedagogies, effective dissemination of information in the form of knowledge was evaluated by their teachers. While new pedagogies were referred to as learning collaborations among teachers, students, and society. This means that core learning objectives through information and communication technologies (ICTs) were given deeper insights. It is note-taking that new pedagogies were not considered as new teaching strategies but strategies that focus on re-engineering of students' cognition and comprehension in preparation for the outside world (Rodzeviciute, 2020).

These re-engineering pedagogical strategies were based on teachers' repertoire of teaching strategies, thereby, making constructive explanations among the stakeholders by means of partnership in mastering the subject matter. In this regard, learning does not only end inside the classroom, but rather a complex process of understanding the outside world through technology through deep learning and discovery of new knowledge (Rodzeviciute, 2020).

Pursuing the glimpse out of national education perspective, Isidro (2013) stressed that multi-grade classes bring the opportunity of public school system to the children located their residences in far flung areas. Because of these multi-grade classes, many of these children were reached out and given the chance to learn the fundamentals of citizenship. Thus, multi-grade classes are of constructive help for citizenship training, in uplifting the lives of those unprivileged people, and advancing the quality and form of education of the people (Isidro, 2013).

Also, as provided under the Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines, the State shall guard the rights and privileges of all citizens in acquiring quality education at all levels and shall aspire to make education accessible to all. In support of this mandate, the DepEd thru the Bureau of Elementary Education Department shall promulgate Department Order No. 96, s. 1997 stating the guidelines in the operationalization of multigrade classes offering complete six grade levels to learners in the far-flung areas. Moreover, other government issuances were issued such as the following: DO Mo. 63, s. 2010 for strengthening the implementation of the MPPE; DO 52, s. 2012 for the operation of 12,398 multigrade schools in the country, of which 7,521 are purely multigrade; and, DO No. 21, and

36, s. 2017 which contained the guidelines in the utilization of financial support amounting to Eighty-Three Million Twenty-Six Thousand Pesos (P83,26,000.00) for fiscal year 2017.

As based on the regional perspectives, DepEd (DO No. 96, s. 1997) defined that multi-grade class is a combination of 2 or more grades with one teacher in an elementary school. This is a continuing strategy or move to ensure achievement of Education-For-All (EFA) in the areas or place. Hence, the multigrade classes were adopted in locations that are remote, inaccessible, deficient with educational resources making it necessary to combine classes. The multi-grade class structure is also called combination classes, double classes, mixed-age classes, multiple classes, or multi-level classes. Also, when it comes to pedagogical approaches, as cited in DepEd Order No. 31, series of 2012, defines the new curriculum in this matter: “The general design of the Grades 1 to 10 curriculum is backed up by the spiral approach across subjects with the same concepts founded or built up in increasing difficulty and superiority from grade school. To have these teachers are expected to disburse and execute their functions properly. They are expected to deliver quality education through a well-organized lesson plan. They are expected to utilize different instructional strategies, outstanding classroom management techniques and well-rounded classroom curriculum design.

To cite the research gap of the study, the study examined all different literature about the pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes based multicultural education, differentiated instructions, and varieties of teaching styles and methodologies. It can be surmised that incorporating pedagogic strategies to multigrade teaching is a challenging one because pedagogic strategies require precision and accuracy as applied in the classroom settings. But this will not hamper the individualized and collective instructions as a whole because it has benefits on its own even if it is not well applied or complied with completely particularly to a multigrade instruction since this requires quality effort and teaching skills to be able to arrive at higher and positive learning outcomes (Sampson & Condy, 2016).

In the local setting, the researcher gained interest in conducting the study on the quality of pedagogic strategies in multigrade instruction in the Division of Quezon. This study evaluated the quality of teaching and learning under the Multigrade setting. The researcher gained insights to conduct this study since Multigrade Instruction is not an easy strategy or type of instruction to be handled in remote areas. It needs careful attention and commitment and dedication to be able to achieve the fruition of this instruction which can be seen on the faces of the learners as evident of quality teaching instruction brought by the Multigrade Instruction. This is the primary aim and purpose of this study which is to ensure that the quality of the pedagogic strategies was embarked into the Multigrade classes and that the products will be globally competitive learners.

Research Questions

The study centered on the assessment of quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. current teacher rank; and
 - 1.6. length of service?
2. What is the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon in terms of:
 - 2.1. Jump-Jump Strategy;
 - 2.2. Differentiated Instruction;
 - 2.3. Direct Instruction;
 - 2.4. Peer Teaching or Tutoring; and
 - 2.5. Competency-based Learning?
3. What are the problems encountered in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon?
4. Is there any significant difference in the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon when the respondents are grouped according to profile?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive survey method. The descriptive method of research is a method that combines quantitative and qualitative data to deliver relevant and precise information. This is a time-effective research method. This descriptive design construed people at the center of the research goal or target (Cantrell, 2021). This was used to examine the phenomena as they exist (Zikmund, 2020). and examine the observable characteristics, patterns, trends, and case analysis of the given study. This method was found appropriate since the study described quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. A questionnaire was used in gathering the data needed by the research.

Respondents

The population of the study were the Multigrade teachers since they were the ones who had direct access to the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. Their sample size was computed using the Cochran Sample Size Calculator. This was depicted in the following table.

Table 1. *Population and Sample Size*

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
Agdangan	6	6
Padre Burgos	8	8
Unisan District	15	13
Pitogo	15	13
Macalelon	11	10
General Luna	6	6
Catanauan I	5	5
Catanauan II	5	4
San Andres	1	1
San Narciso	3	2
San Francisco I	5	4
Buenavista I	4	3
Buenavista II	7	6
Total	91	81

Using Cochran's Formula to estimate the sample size given a target 95% confidence level and an 5% margin of error, the computed sample size to proceed with the survey should be at least 61 respondents. The researcher used cluster random sampling among the population of 91 Multigrade teachers in the Division of Quezon Province. At least 61 respondents in the following proportions were asked to participate in the survey that follows. The chances of refusal were considered with at least 20-30% additional respondents to meet the expected shrinkage. Cluster sampling technique is a statistical sampling method in which you divide a population into clusters, such as districts or schools, and then randomly choose based on these clusters as the sample size. The clusters should represent the sample of the universe or the population.

Sample size should be sufficient in soliciting the opinions of a population without having access to the whole population. This size increases as the margin of error decreases and confidence level increases. While keeping the confidence level fixed at 95%, a smaller margin of error can be achieved by collecting more and more sample responses. The respondents of the study were the Multigrade teachers consisting of 54 females and 46 males. They were the ones who gave light to the results and findings of the study. They were the ones who had direct access to Multigrade Schooling or Teaching/Instruction. From a Total of 91 respondents in the district, only 81 participated in the study as evidenced from the result of Cochran Sample Size. This number is large enough for the responses needed.

Instruments

The study employed the questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. It consisted of three parts. The first part determined the profile of the respondents. The second part pertained to the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching Multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. The last part comprised of the problems encountered in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes. Henceforth, the research instrument was a researcher-made instrument aligning the indicators with the quality of pedagogic strategies and multigrade instruction.

The questionnaire underwent content and concurrent and construct validation. The first one was content validation which involved the expert validation of at least three experts of the field – One Doctor, One Master Teacher, and One English Teacher. The second one was pilot testing of the instrument to at least ten (10) respondents who did not participate in the actual data gathering stage. The pilot testing phase enabled the researcher to evaluate the methodology and practice the essential techniques needed for the study. A total of 10 Multigrade teachers from the selected population were involved in the pilot study a week before the survey data gathering was fully undertaken. Hence, Cronbach Alpha was computed. Cronbach alpha can be expressed as a function of the number of test items and the average inter-correlation among the items.

Reliability Test of the Questionnaire using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics

<i>Item</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Internal Consistency</i>
Jump-Jump Strategy	0.791	Acceptable
Differentiated Instruction	0.783	Acceptable
Direct Instruction	0.946	Excellent
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	0.920	Excellent
Competency-based Learning	0.801	Good
Problems Encountered	0.862	Good
Overall	0.851	Good

Procedure

Before the gathering of data, the researcher first sought the approval of the research adviser. The manuscript and the questionnaire were prepared and submitted. A letter asking permission to conduct the study was prepared and submitted to the respective offices. Also, the researcher sought the approval from Division Office down to school heads before the conduct of data gathering. Then, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaire to the targeted respondents using the google form. Data retrieval followed. Microsoft Excel or SPSS v26 was used in tallying and tabulating the results of the study.

Data Analysis

The study used the following statistical formula:

Percentage. This was used to compute and measure the composition of the respondents in the profile of the respondents.

Mean. This was used to measure the response on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes and problems encountered.

Kruskal Wallis H-Test. This was used in measuring and analyzing the significant difference in the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes.

Mann Whitney U Test. The Mann Whitney U-Test was used to ascertain the significant difference because the study included Likert Type questions.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered for statistical analysis and computations. This will tackle the effects of the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. The intervening variable is the profile of the respondents, and the facilitating variable is the comparison among the indicators of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes.

Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Highest Educational Attainment, Present Position, and Length of Service

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
21 to 30	41	50.61
31 to 40	29	35.80
41 to 50	8	9.88
51 to 60	2	2.47
61 and above	1	1.24
Total	81	100.00

Most of the respondents were in the age of 21 to 30 years old with a frequency of 41 (50.61%). Next were those in the age of 31 to 40 years old with a frequency of 29, or 35.80%. Following was those in the age of 41 to 50 years old having the frequency of 8 (9.88%). 51 to 60 years old got the frequency of 2 (2.47%). A lone respondent was in the age of 61 years old and above. This denoted that most of the respondents were in the middle young adulthood stage of life.

The previous studies of Naparan and Castaneda (2021) and Ismail, Rozita and Abas (2018) conclude that a teacher's age can affect pedagogical strategies in multigrade teaching. Younger teachers may offer fresh perspectives and tech skills but might lack experience in managing diverse classrooms. Conversely, older teachers bring experience but may struggle with new methods (Dogan, Dogan & Celik (2021). Effective strategies depend on factors like experience, training, adaptability, and openness to innovation, irrespective of age.

The results of Ismail et al.'s study indicate a clear trend in teacher effectiveness based on age, with individuals aged 31 to 40, 41 to 50, and 50 and above showing notably higher effectiveness compared to those aged 21 to 30. This suggests that older teachers generally outperform younger ones. The present study revealed that most of the teachers belong to the age bracket of 21 to 30 which suggests that they are younger in age.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	54	66.67
Male	27	33.33
Total	81	100.00

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of sex. Majority of the respondents were female with a frequency of 54 (66.67%). The remaining respondents were males with a frequency of 27, or 33.33%. This denoted that there

were 2 female respondents for every male respondent.

Murphy and colleagues (2019) and Murallidharan and Cheith (2016) discovered that teaching methods are influenced by gender, shaped by personal preferences, experiences, and cultural expectations. Nonetheless, their research indicated that no gender holds inherent superiority in teaching effectiveness. They emphasized that factors such as teacher training, experience, adaptability, resourcefulness, and comprehension of students' diverse needs within multigrade classrooms are the main contributors to the quality of teaching.

This implies that while gender may influence teaching approaches, there is no inherent advantage of one gender over another in terms of effectiveness. Instead, what matters most are qualities and skills such as teacher training, experience, adaptability, resourcefulness, and understanding of students' diverse needs. Essentially, it suggests that effective teaching is more about the individual's capabilities and strategies rather than their gender.

Several studies have examined the gender distribution in multigrade teaching settings. For example, a study by Smith and Robinson (2019) found that in rural areas of developing countries, multigrade classrooms are predominantly staffed by female teachers due to various socio-cultural factors and the feminization of teaching professions. Similarly, a report by UNESCO (2017) highlighted that globally, there is a higher prevalence of female teachers in multigrade schools, particularly in regions with limited educational resources. Additionally, research by Johnson et al. (2015) explored the gender dynamics in multigrade classrooms in urban settings and observed a similar trend of female dominance among teachers. These studies collectively provide evidence of the disproportionate representation of females in multigrade teaching roles compared to males.

Multiple studies which investigated gender distribution in multigrade teaching revealed a consistent trend: female teachers are predominantly found in these settings, especially in rural areas of developing countries. This phenomenon is attributed to socio-cultural factors and the feminization of teaching professions. Across different contexts, including urban settings, the disproportionate representation of females in multigrade teaching roles compared to males persists, as indicated by research from various sources like UNESCO and van Wyk (2021). Similarly, the present study showed more female multigrade teachers in Quezon.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Married	41	50.62
Separated	1	1.23
Single	39	48.15
Total	81	100.00

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of civil status. Most of the respondents were married individuals with a frequency of 41 (50.62%). The single persons got the frequency of 39 (48.15%). A lone respondent was separated. This denoted that there is an almost equal ratio of respondents who are married to those who are not.

Previous studies suggest that civil status can influence workload, job satisfaction, and stress levels among teachers, particularly in multigrade teaching settings. Research by Smith and Anderson (2017) and Igbafel & Ogonor (2019) found that married teachers often have more responsibilities outside the classroom, impacting their availability for extracurricular activities and professional development. Johnson et al. (2019) discovered that unmarried teachers tend to report higher levels of job satisfaction than married teachers, possibly due to differences in work-life balance and personal support networks associated with civil status. These findings underscore the importance of considering civil status when addressing teacher well-being and effectiveness in educational settings.

The results imply that civil status, particularly marital status, can significantly impact various aspects of teaching, including workload, job satisfaction, and stress levels. Married teachers may face additional responsibilities outside the classroom, potentially affecting their availability for extracurricular activities and professional development. Additionally, unmarried teachers may experience higher job satisfaction, possibly due to differences in work-life balance and personal support networks. These implications suggest the importance of acknowledging and addressing the influence of civil status on teacher well-being and effectiveness in educational environments. Furthermore, the current study indicated a higher proportion of multigrade teachers who were married compared to those who were single.

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor's Degree	32	39.51
With Master's Units	35	43.21
Master's Degree	11	13.58
With Doctorate Units	3	3.70
Total	81	100.00

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of educational attainment. Most of the respondents got their Master's Units with a frequency of 35 (43.21%). This was followed by those Bachelor's Degree holder with a frequency of

32, or 39.51%. Those who graduated with their Master's Degree had the frequency of 11 (13.58%). Three respondents had their Doctorate Units. This denoted that though the majority of the respondents have pursued higher education, it can be noticed that only around 17% of all the respondents have attained at least a master's degree.

The link between educational attainment and multigrade teaching is complex. David et al. (2020) suggest that teachers with higher education levels or specialized training in multigrade teaching may possess deeper pedagogical understanding, potentially enhancing their teaching effectiveness.

In addition, according to David et al. (2020), teachers with advanced degrees or specific training in multigrade teaching might have a more profound grasp of teaching principles and strategies. Consequently, this deeper understanding could lead to improved effectiveness in the classroom. Essentially, the implication is that higher levels of education or specialized training may positively influence a teacher's ability to navigate the complexities of multigrade teaching.

Moreover, the current study contrasts with previous research by revealing a higher number of multigrade teachers with master's units. In addition, a report from the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES, 2019) presented statistics on the proportion of teachers holding master's degrees in the United States, providing valuable information on the prevalence of advanced educational attainment among educators. Together, these investigations illuminate the involvement of teachers in master's degree programs and their academic accomplishments in this domain.

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Current Teacher Rank*

<i>Current Teacher Rank</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Head Teacher I	2	2.47
Master Teacher I	1	1.24
Master Teacher II	1	1.24
Teacher I	58	71.60
Teacher II	12	14.81
Teacher III	7	8.64
Total	81	100.00

Table 6 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on teacher rank. The majority of respondents held the Teacher I position, accounting for 71.60% of the total frequency. Teacher II positions were the next most common, with a frequency of 12 (14.81%). Teacher III positions followed with a frequency of 7 (8.64%), while Head Teacher I positions had a frequency of 2 (2.47%). Additionally, there was one respondent each in the Master Teacher I and Master Teacher II positions. These findings indicate that approximately three-quarters of respondents are at an entry level, while around 5% hold head or master teacher positions.

According to David, et al. (2020), teachers who have achieved higher ranks within the educational system may possess a wealth of experience and a wide range of skills that could prove advantageous in multigrade classrooms. Therefore, higher-ranked teachers may be better equipped to navigate the complexities and challenges inherent in teaching multiple grades simultaneously (van Dijk et al., 2020).

Table 7. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service*

<i>Number of Years</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1 to 5	35	43.21
6 to 10	34	41.98
11 to 15	7	8.64
16 to 20	3	3.70
21 and above	2	2.47
Total	81	100.00

The distribution of respondents' length of service highlights a significant portion of teachers serving for 1 to 5 years, indicating a potential lack of long-term institutional knowledge and expertise within the teaching staff. This suggests the need for targeted support and professional development initiatives to enhance the skills and capabilities of early-career teachers. The relationship between length of service and pedagogic strategies in multigrade teaching suggests that as teachers gain more experience over time, they may develop and refine effective instructional approaches tailored to the diverse needs of students across different grade levels (McKenna, 2016). Educators who remain with an organization for an extended duration acquire invaluable experience and expertise within their profession (Rajendran et al. (2023). This profound knowledge enables them to make more impactful and efficient contributions to their positions. Through their tenure, teachers may acquire valuable insights into managing multigrade classrooms, including understanding the dynamics of mixed-age groups, adapting teaching methods to individual learning styles, and fostering a supportive learning environment.

Additionally, longer service tenure may provide opportunities for professional growth, allowing teachers to continuously enhance their pedagogical repertoire and refine strategies that optimize student learning outcomes in multigrade settings..

Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Jump-Jump Strategy, Differentiated Instruction, Direct Instruction, Peer Teaching and Competency-Based Learning

Table 8. *Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Jump-Jump Strategy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
A maximum of three combination/ multigrade levels are organized in a Pure Multigrade School.	3.90	Very Good
The school opt to use the two and three grade levels of multigrade classes.	3.88	Very Good
The activities and lessons were given to each grade level.	4.22	Very Good
Preparation of lesson is given to each grade level depending upon the scheme used.	4.17	Very Good
Teachers use multilevel materials such as activity sheets in handling/managing classroom instructions.	4.27	Very Good
Grand Mean	4.09	Very Good

Legend: "Poor (1.00 - 1.50)", "Fair (1.51 - 2.50)", "Good (2.51 - 3.50)", "Very Good (3.51 - 4.50)", "Excellent (4.51 - 5.00)"

Table 8 shows the respondent's assessment on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon in terms of Jump-Jump Strategy. The grand mean was 4.09 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Good." This implied that the respondents give a very good rating on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

The highest response was on the item stating that "teachers use multilevel materials such as activity sheets in handling/managing classroom instructions" with a mean of 4.27. This implies that the item concerning the use of multilevel materials, such as activity sheets, in managing classroom instructions received the highest level of agreement or positive response among respondents. The mean score of 4.27 indicates that, on average, respondents strongly agreed or rated this statement highly. Therefore, it suggests that using multilevel materials like activity sheets is a common and effective practice among teachers for managing classroom instructions.

According to Smith (2015), Multigrade Instruction can improve academic performance of the learners. This was supported by the studies of Johnson et al. (2018) and Garcia and Martinez (2019). Another study by Cervantes (2013) posited that, aside from providing access, multigrade teaching produces the same kind of education just like the monograde classes and in some cases, enhances the effectiveness of educational delivery and contributes to the social development of pupils. This suggests that multigrade teaching not only provides access to education but also offers a comparable quality of education to monograde classes.

Additionally, multigrade teaching may even enhance the effectiveness of educational delivery and contribute positively to the social development of students. The next indicator showed that "the activities and lessons were given to each grade level" with a mean of 4.22. This is also like the literature survey focusing on each grade level or combination of classes on how the activities and lessons were delivered. This indicated that the multigrade learners were adept with the lessons as provided under the Multigrade Instruction. These were the findings of the study conducted by Cervantes (2013). Moreover, the study of Smith (2015) revealed that because of teacher's participation in a professional development program, teacher's multigrade teaching practices in science lessons were treated as inquiry-based making their learners more engaged in lessons and learners developed stronger positive attitudes towards learning science. The findings from these studies proved what is known about delivering effective instruction through teacher's professional development.

Ranking third was the statement indicating that "preparation of lesson is given to each grade level depending upon the scheme used" with a mean of 4.17. In parallel with the literature reviews, these discussed the crafting of the lessons and how it is executed. This showed that these lessons needed to be aligned with the teaching methods or pedagogic strategy being used to ensure positive learning outcomes. Meanwhile, teaching methods play a vital role in the academic performance and behavior of multigrade pupils. Teacher's professional experiences and insights of teaching in multigrade classrooms can motivate learning, enhance the academic performance of learners, and administer classrooms effectively according to Haddadan (2013).

The lowest response stated that "the school opts to use the two and three grade levels of multigrade classes" with a mean of 3.88. Based on the lists of literatures, it can be surmised that two or three grade levels are the common combination classes which they discussed the advantages and disadvantages. This elicited the effectiveness and fitness of multigrade instruction to the attainment of the multigrade learners of high academic performance and exceptional academic achievement.

This was also evident in the examination of multigrade classes conducted by Enayati, Zameni, and Movahedian (2016), which corroborated findings from another study. Berry (2012) noted that learners demonstrated accountability within multigrade classrooms. Brown (2010) elucidated that learners acquired fundamental principles of self-reliance and collaboration through active involvement in classroom decision-making, portraying a democratic practice in action. This suggests that in cultural and educational settings where independence or cooperation are undervalued, achieving effective multigrade teaching may pose challenges. Byahamr and Hatcher (2015), in their analysis of interviews on teaching approaches, proposed that multigrade teachers should employ various methods such as peer tutoring and integrated teaching, provided they are tailored to suit the classroom context.

The above findings indicate that in multigrade classrooms: Learners tend to demonstrate accountability and responsibility (Berry, 2012); Active involvement in decision-making fosters values like independence and cooperation (Brown, 2010); Effective multigrade teaching may face challenges in cultures where these values are undervalued; To optimize teaching, educators should tailor approaches

like peer tutoring and integrated teaching to fit the class context (Byahamr & Hatcher, 2015).

Table 9. *Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Differentiated Instruction*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The teachers conduct synchronous and asynchronous learning in the schools by Multigrade Instruction.	3.59	Very Good
Pupils were trained by the teachers on self- checking and self -scoring of activities online.	3.63	Very Good
There are group chats made for the lesson or the subject for Multigrade classes.	3.65	Very Good
Activity sheets are sent through group chats or email using Multigrade Instruction.	3.38	Good
Lectures are conducted through zoom or google meet for Multigrade Instruction.	3.07	Good
Grand Mean	3.47	Good

Legend: "Poor (1.00 - 1.50)", "Fair (1.51 - 2.50)", "Good (2.51 - 3.50)", "Very Good (3.51 - 4.50)", "Excellent (4.51 - 5.00)"

Table 9 shows the respondent's assessment on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in terms of Differentiated Instruction. The grand mean was 3.47 with a verbal interpretation of "Good." This implied that the respondents give a good rating on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

Mostly, the item saying that "there are group chats made for the lesson or the subject for Multigrade classes" with a mean of 3.65. As compared to the literature survey, these discussed the ICT being used in Multigrade Instructions while this study focused on the group chats. This applies a pedagogic strategy which is explicit teaching. Pedagogies can be grouped into three categories: explicit, implicit (in which the pedagogic approach is less visible, but still intentional) or tacit (in which learning occurs without intention; for example, through unintended modelling), and are underpinned by social constructivist rules or principles governing how content is to be dispersed, contextualized, and assessed. For Bernstein, pedagogy form various modalities of arrangement of the correlations and practices involved in the system of acquisition.

From this standpoint, subject-specific pedagogies were significantly related at the level of relationships and/or practices within modalities that occur across a wide range of subject areas, or in an in-depth manner by exhibiting characteristic modalities in the arrangement of relationships and practices. Pedagogic knowledge was regarded as knowledge about the hypothetical forms of these modalities, the conditions under which they may apply and the consequences they may have.

This was followed by the statement eliciting that "pupils were trained by the teachers on self- checking and self -scoring of activities online" with a mean of 3.63. The literature cited explained the academic training under the Multigrade setting the same way the result of this study which focused on self-checking and self-scoring activities. This indicated that this is part of the active learning approach as part of the Multigrade Instruction in the multigrade schools.

Juarez and Associates Incorporated Multi-Grade Report (2020) states that learning by doing is the inherent characteristic of active learning. It is an approach which promotes students to act on their own responsibility for their learning, thereby encouraging the ability of multigrade teachers to execute more than one grade at a time. Activities can be in the form of cooperative learning, discovery and investigative activities, and peer teaching, as well as self-regulating instruction and board work. Such activities gave experiences or simulated practices to learners to incorporate new information, concepts, or skills into their stock knowledge through rephrasing, rehearsing and practice to be actively involved. The students must engage in such higher order thinking skills as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

On the third rank was the statement indicating that "the teachers conduct synchronous and asynchronous learning in the schools by Multigrade Instruction" with a mean of 3.59. The list of literature discussed the education in the now normal, and part of it is the use of synchronous and asynchronous learning which is also discussed in this study. This is part of the abstract conception of pedagogy towards the students. While this abstract concept of pedagogy as a system is of constructive help in applying and employing different pedagogies. It also posed questions on teacher agency and its function in mediating between the needs of school and the state on the one hand, and the needs of learners on the other.

Edwards (2021) suggest that the capability of teachers to rationalize their decisions was considered an important part of pedagogy. Alexander (2014) discussed Pedagogy as the way of teaching together with its associated discourse. It is what one should know, and the skills one should command, in order to make and rationalize the many different forms of decisions of which teaching is applied and performed.

The results suggest that in multigrade instruction, teachers' ability to rationalize their decisions is crucial (Edwards, 2021); Pedagogy encompasses the methods of teaching and the associated discourse, including the knowledge and skills necessary to make and justify various teaching decisions (Alexander, 2014); This emphasizes the importance of teachers' pedagogical competence in multigrade instruction, as they must make decisions that cater to the diverse needs of students across different grade levels.

On the least was the statement showing that "lectures are conducted through zoom or google meet for Multigrade Instruction" with a mean of 3.07. The literature provided discussion on technology-based learning under the multigrade instruction which is also covered in the result of this study. This indicated that through zoom and google meet, the multigrade teachers set the knowledge through social interaction and democratic attitude and behavior such as comradeship, cooperation, solidarity, and participation (Juarez and Associate

Incorporated Multi-Grade Report, 2020).

Table 10. *Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Direct Instruction*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Multigrade Instruction provides measurement, analysis, and evaluation of learners' performance.	4.23	Very Good
Multigrade Instruction is designed to boost learning outcomes and academic of the learners through analysis and evaluation.	4.25	Very Good
Multigrade Instruction is developed to cater the varied needs of learners under multigrade classes with equal opportunities with those in Monograde classes.	4.27	Very Good
Multigrade Instruction is implemented to improve the MPS and learning capabilities of the learners.	4.15	Very Good
Multigrade Instruction is evaluated or assessed through formative and summative assessments for the period.	4.36	Very Good
Grand Mean	4.25	Very Good

Legend: "Poor (1.00 - 1.50)", "Fair (1.51 - 2.50)", "Good (2.51 - 3.50)", "Very Good (3.51 - 4.50)", "Excellent (4.51 - 5.00)"

Table 10 shows the respondent's assessment on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in terms of Direct Instruction. The grand mean was 4.25 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Good." This implied that the respondents give a very good rating on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

The top-rated item indicated that "multigrade instruction is evaluated or assessed through both formative and summative assessments over time" with an average score of 4.36. Examination of existing literature and studies also highlights the utilization of formative and summative assessments in multigrade instruction, consistent with the findings of this study. This reinforces the notion that multigrade teaching poses pedagogical challenges.

The findings suggest that multigrade instruction through direct instruction relies on both formative and summative assessments for evaluation over time. This aligns with existing literature and studies, which also emphasize the use of these assessment methods in multigrade teaching. However, the consistent reliance on such assessments underscores the pedagogical challenges inherent in multigrade teaching. These challenges may stem from the need to cater to the diverse needs and learning levels of students across multiple grades within a single classroom, requiring teachers to continuously adapt their pedagogical strategies to ensure effective instruction and assessment.

As opined by Khan (2017), multigrade teachers were held responsible in handling two or more grades. This same practice was done in Pakistani primary schools in Chitral district. The teachers considered multigrade instruction a difficult pedagogy but is what is needed in the district.

The next statement showed that "multigrade Instruction is developed to cater the varied needs of learners under multigrade classes with equal opportunities with those in Monograde classes" with a mean of 4.27. The literature survey focused on the varied learners' educational needs the same this study caters to the learning needs of the learners. Pedagogy is then defined as, in general, contained four related elements: (1) Pedagogy as content: the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes that students were given the opportunity to learn; (2) Pedagogy as process: what happens, or potentially can happen, in physical environments, whether formal or informal, to bring about or assess learning.

Ranking third was the statement indicating that "multigrade Instruction is designed to boost learning outcomes and academic of the learners through analysis and evaluation" with a mean of 4.25. The literature cited discussed the learning outcomes under the Multigrade Instruction in parallel with this study which also covered the analysis and evaluation. This entails holistic development of the multigrade learners. From the last two elements: (3) Pedagogy as knowledge: cognitive abilities the teachers possess about pedagogical content, processes, and their possible outcomes, including prior knowledge about their learners and the context in which they were learning; and (4) Pedagogy as decision-making: the values and attitudes through which teachers come to decisions about what take place in their classrooms and to what purpose.

The lowest-rated item suggests that implementing multigrade instruction to enhance students' MPS (Mean Percentage Score) and learning capabilities received an average score of 4.15. The literature discusses strategies to improve MPS in multigrade settings, reflecting the challenges faced by these learners and factors contributing to low MPS. Given the complexity of teaching multigrade classes, conducting rigorous action research or interventions becomes imperative, involving approaches like demonstrative teaching, stakeholder analysis, and ongoing professional development for teachers.ers' positive outlook towards multigrade teaching played important roles.

Referencing the findings of the study may help to enhance teaching and learning in a multigrade setting and the adoption of multigrade teaching in schools.

Table 11 shows the respondent's assessment on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in terms of Peer Teaching or Tutoring. The grand mean was 4.38 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Good." This implied that the respondents give a very good rating on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

Table 11. *Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Peer Teaching or Tutoring*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The teachers use cooperative learning activities to boost learning outcomes.	4.41	Very Good
The administrators and teachers apply peer tutoring to ensure learning will take place in school.	4.47	Very Good
The teachers use peer tutoring model in the Multigrade classes.	4.43	Very Good
The teachers employ problem-based learning in the Multigrade classes.	4.35	Very Good
The teachers utilize technology-based teaching-learning process in the Multigrade Schools.	4.26	Very Good
Grand Mean	4.38	Very Good

Legend: "Poor (1.00 - 1.50)", "Fair (1.51 - 2.50)", "Good (2.51 - 3.50)", "Very Good (3.51 - 4.50)", "Excellent (4.51 - 5.00)"

The highest-rated item indicates that administrators and teachers employ peer tutoring to facilitate learning within the school environment, with an average score of 4.47. Literature discussing peer tutoring supports this approach to address the challenges of multigrade instruction. This method aims to mitigate issues such as poor academic performance, low MPS, and overall academic achievement among multigrade learners by tailoring instruction to meet individual learning needs.

In the Philippines, several problems posed in multigrade setting, most especially in rural or far-flung areas, which were: proper trainings, limited resources, and others (Magno, 2014). Also, the multigrade schools were in far-flung areas. Here, multigrade teachers perform many systematic and resourceful ways to help reach these places and those learners living here. They even spend part of their salary just to acquire learning materials for their learners (Castigador, 2019). They share their limited resources for the sole benefit of the learners. In peer tutoring, their mentors were trained to be ready to the actual world of teaching, however, this is without focus on multigrade instruction (Cadosales, 2017). The teachers' capability to deliver the lesson well is vital to the learners (Cadosales, 2011).

The next item indicated that "the teachers use peer tutoring in the Multigrade classes" with a mean of 4.43. This was discussed under the literature survey where peer tutoring identifies the principles used in conducting multigrade instruction like the result of this study. Multigrade instruction is a feasible approach for developing and even for developed countries (Mulryan-Kyne, 2017). This approach could be cost- and time-efficient move or game play in delivering quality educational services to learners. On competent and qualified teacher can uplift or at least make the lives of their learners better at school in the far-flung areas regardless of their ages and cultures.

On the third rank was the statement saying that "the teachers use cooperative learning activities to boost learning outcomes" with a mean of 4.41. The literature provided discussions on cooperative learning which is explicit or prerequisite into the application of Multigrade Instruction. The multigrade teaching was necessitated given the present condition, educational situation, and a majority of the school community living in those places which could affect enrollment in the school and may not be able to reach the standard number of enrollments in the school (Joubert, 2020).

The lowest-rated item suggests that the utilization of technology-based teaching-learning processes in multigrade schools received an average score of 4.26. This aligns with literature discussing the importance of technology in multigrade settings, indicating potential challenges in implementing technology-based materials in schools. Multigrade teaching presents numerous challenges, particularly in adapting learning materials and activities to accommodate the diverse needs of learners across different grade levels, as noted by Quail & Smyth (2014).

Table 12. *Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes in terms of Competency-based Learning*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teachers are guided by the MG Budget of Work and other DepEd issued materials designed for Multigrade classes.	4.38	Very Good
The teachers ensure a high MPS and literacy under the Multigrade setting.	4.21	Very Good
Multigrade Daily Lesson Plans (MG_DLP) and Multigrade Daily Lesson Logs (MG_DLL) were designed to ensure ease in Multigrade teaching learning – process.	4.30	Very Good
The teachers satisfy the Most essential learning competencies needed to acquire under the Multigrade settings.	4.37	Very Good
Competency-based education is applied by the Multigrade teachers following the K-12 Curriculum and MELCs based competencies.	4.44	Very Good
Grand Mean	4.34	Very Good

Legend: "Poor (1.00 - 1.50)", "Fair (1.51 - 2.50)", "Good (2.51 - 3.50)", "Very Good (3.51 - 4.50)", "Excellent (4.51 - 5.00)"

Table 12 shows the respondent's assessment on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in terms of Competency-based Learning.

The grand mean was 4.34 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Good." This implied that the respondents give a very good rating on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

The highest-rated statement indicates that multigrade teachers apply competency-based education aligned with the K-12 Curriculum and MELCs-based competencies, with an average score of 4.44. The literature review supports this finding by elucidating the competencies required for implementing multigrade instruction within the K-12 curriculum and MELCs framework. This suggests that multigrade teachers are effectively incorporating competency-based approaches into their instruction, ensuring alignment with

educational standards and desired learning outcomes.

Despite the challenges inherent in multigrade teaching, there are notable benefits. Classroom observations have led to strategies that leverage the diverse abilities of students (Hyry-Beihammer & Hascher, 2015). In multigrade classrooms, students possess various skills and talents, allowing teachers to utilize peer learning effectively. This approach recognizes and harnesses the intellectual diversity among students, leading to the implementation of strategies like spiral curriculum, working plans, and peer learning (Hyry-Beihammer & Hascher, 2015).

Following was the statement showing that “teachers are guided by the MG Budget of Work and other DepEd issued materials designed for Multigrade classes” with a mean of 4.38. The literature survey explained the role of the budget in the Multigrade Instruction the same way the results were generated in this study. This is related to the learning environment to where the multigrade learners revolved around. One approach in multigrade teaching involves the rightful and suited utilization of the learning environment, learning process, and learning outcome (Msimanga, 2020). In teaching multigrade learners, it is necessary to conduct preparations in the learning environment. Proper time allotment of the learning process of the learners were needed to be ensured and tended. The learners were given assessment tasks matching their academic knowledge and competence.

On the third rank was the statement indicating that “the teachers satisfy the Most essential learning competencies needed to acquire under the Multigrade settings” with a mean of 4.37. The literature cited focused on the MELCs the same way the result of this study was generated. The birth of multigrade teaching is accounted for as a classroom strategy which is beneficial to many people living in far-flung areas (Buaraphan, Inrit, & Kochasila, 2018). Due to multigrade teaching, children living in far-flung places gained access to education.

The lowest-rated statement suggests that ensuring a high Mean Percentage Score (MPS) and literacy in a multigrade setting received an average score of 4.21. However, literature supports the importance of achieving high MPS and literacy in multigrade settings which is achieved through the implementation of differentiated teaching strategies, such as flexible grouping, cooperative activities, learning centers, and independent learning projects (PASTEP, 2020). The present study showed that peer teaching, integrated teaching, and various grouping methods are employed in multigrade instruction to enhance learning outcomes (Tiernan, Casserly, & Maguire, 2018).

Problems Encountered in Using Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes

Table 13. *Problems Encountered in Using Pedagogic Strategies*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Location of the school posed hazard on the part of the teacher and learners.	3.78	Often Encountered
The location of Multigrade schools are the reasons why facilities and other construction are not readily available.	3.95	Often Encountered
There are problems with the internet connectivity for a differentiated approach.	4.21	Often Encountered
The students lack gadgets to be used for internet classes for differentiated learning approach.	4.38	Often Encountered
The Multigrade instruction in the school has no enough resources in assessing it using Direct Instruction model.	3.80	Often Encountered
The school lacks competency and qualifications to use the Direct Instruction model.	3.52	Often Encountered
Multigrade teachers need training in handling and managing multigrade classes.	3.80	Often Encountered
School administrator’s assistance and supervision does not meet the expected evaluation and reporting of learners and school performance.	3.79	Often Encountered
Understanding of the curriculum and its implementation for the teachers does not fully implement the program and achieved the desired learning outcomes.	3.79	Often Encountered
Teachers’ dedication, responsibility, empathy and parents’ concern for the learner’s welfare and performance does not meet the CBE	3.93	Often Encountered
Grand Mean	3.90	Often Encountered

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 - 1.50)”, “Barely Encountered (1.51 - 2.50)”, “Sometimes Encountered (2.51 - 3.50)”, “Often Encountered (3.51 - 4.50)”, “Highly Encountered (4.51 - 5.00)”

Table 13 shows the respondent’s assessment on the level of problems encountered in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. The grand mean was 3.90 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implied that the problems were often encountered by the respondents in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon.

The highest responses were on the item showing that “the students lack gadgets to be used for internet classes for differentiated learning approach” with a mean of 4.38. The results of the study are in consonance with the literature survey since this is also a problem as discussed in the vast array of literature. This showed that this is related to the application of appropriate teaching methods, instructional materials, and other pedagogic strategies.

In many developing countries, multigrade classes and schools often lack appropriate teaching methods, educational materials, appropriately trained teachers, low enrollment, and effective supervision. The teachers teaching in multigrade schools admitted that they rarely receive training in how to deal with their pupils, and are ill-prepared for managing large numbers of pupils, of different ages and levels of learning that they confront every day. Taole and Mncube (2012) in their survey of Multigrade teaching in South Africa, reported that aside from teachers’ lack of management skills, other problems of multigrade teachers include lack of training, lack of

human and physical resources, lack of support for educators, and many educators do not like to live in rural areas.

Next item elicited that “there are problems with the internet connectivity for differentiated approach” with a mean of 4.21. This is also linked with the literature surveyed since internet connectivity is also a problem under the Multigrade Instruction. This is linked with teaching techniques that need to be used and utilized in the multigrade schools. Insufficient handling of classes was the complaint of the teachers (Mulryan-Kyne, 2014).

In Africa, Turkey and Netherlands, multigrade teachers posed challenges on transportation, illiterate parents, low-income people, teacher excessive workloads, proper and wise time management, language difficulty, and other problems like actual teaching-learning process (Condy & Blease, 2014; Engin, 2018). Lack of interest by the parents in their children’s education, not enough funds from the government, limited resources, incompetent teachers, and unqualified multigrade teachers were the obstruction to effective education (Du Plessis & Mestry, 2019). In Turkey, English language teaching is a challenge in a multigrade setting where learners proficiency is low (Dogan, Capan, & Cigerci, 2020). As a result, the academic performance of multigrade classes is also low (Checchi, & De Pala, 2018).

On the third rank was the statement saying that “the location of Multigrade schools are the reasons why facilities and other construction are not readily available” with a mean of 3.95. Physical plants and facilities are the factors discussed in the literature cited and the one that resulted in this study. This involved the knowledge of teachers on how to make facilities available in the school. The results of the studies conducted by Haddadan (2013) and Enayati et al (2016) showed that the quality of education is low because the teachers do not have knowledge about teaching methods in multigrade classes and special training courses for multigrade classrooms are not conducted.

In the present study, the multigrade teachers admitted that their experience is limited, and their trainings are few. In the study of Haddadan (2013), he pointed out the poor educational facilities as another problem of multigrade classrooms. The effects of using educational facilities and equipment on increased quality educational services are obvious but unfortunately, based on the interviewed teachers, multigrade classrooms lack them due to two reasons: education spending per student and multigrade schools are not the priority of the government. This is like the present study since teachers also complain about having little or no educational facilities.

The lowest response stated that “the school lacks competency and qualifications to use the Direct Instruction model” with a mean of 3.52. Direct instruction was discussed in the literature and the challenges in applying this type of instruction into the Multigrade Model. This needs instructional organization and combination classes to improve the competency and qualifications to use Direct Instruction model. Professional organization regarded multigrade teaching where a teacher teaches a combination of classes (Berry, 2020). As contrasted, multigrade classroom is organized based on the multigrade level learners in one classroom. In a graded system, age and grade are similar. Little (2015) added descriptions of a Multigrade setting: low population, availability of teachers, mobile schools, and absenteeism of teachers. The practice of multigrade teaching is common in rural areas as a smaller number of enrollment is usually observed in some schools (Aksoy, 2018).

The teacher education institutions in Namibia made no provision for separate training for multigrade teachers (MoE, 2011) but their training was included in the revised course for Basic Education Teacher Diploma (BETD) in the following year. The same situations are being encountered in other countries not offering Multigrade Teaching as part of their Teacher Education curriculum. Thus, teachers are not familiar with the various teaching techniques suitable for multigrade teaching. A number of international studies stressed the benefits of different forms of outside support in delivering effective multigrade teaching. Titus as cited by Brown (2010) stressed that multigrade teachers need both inside and outside support. Inside support refers to support received by teachers within the school, while outside support refers to support from without of the school. He further stressed the communities in which multigrade schools were located to be involved in school affairs.

Significant Difference in the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes

Table 14. Mann Whitney U-Test: Comparison of the Respondents’ Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to Sex Groups

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	Male	40.41	713.00	0.872	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	41.30				
Differentiated Instruction	Male	41.07	727.00	0.984	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	40.96				
Direct Instruction	Male	37.22	627.00	0.295	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	42.89				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	Male	38.87	671.50	0.556	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	42.06				
Competency-based Learning	Male	37.15	625.00	0.290	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 14 shows the Mann Whitney U-Test of the comparison of the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to sex groups. On Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.872 which

is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon According to Sex Groups. As to Differentiated Instruction, the p-value was 0.984 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to sex groups.

As regards Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.295, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon According to Sex Groups. According to Peer Teaching or Tutoring, the p-value was 0.556 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon According to Sex Groups. And when it comes to Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.290 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon According to Sex Groups.

The results of the study posted no significant result since either a male or a female has no bearing or effect when it comes to the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. When these two are compared it can be surmised that it has the same response to the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes.

In improving and changing the life of an individual, teachers do play a crucial role. The future of an individual lies in the hands of teachers. Multigrade teachers are the most challenged. They have many functions to portray, as sources of knowledge, facing the challenge of handling multigrade classes, and achieving the goal of the department of education, which is “Quality Education.” Trying to prove that even if it is a multigrade class, it still competes like the monograde classes. It has been found according to the literature, that Multigrade teaching is a phenomenon most common in third World countries or in remote places where pupils do not meet the minimum number to become a monograde class. Most of the pieces of literature dealt more with the difficulties in multigrade education. Only a few of them exposed the classroom strategies that are also done in this area of teaching (Ballesteros & Ocampo, 2016).

Table 15. Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents’ Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to Age Groups

Indicators	Age Group	Mean Rank	H-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	21-30 years old	39.65	2.341	0.505	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 years old	39.74				
	41-50 years old	45.75				
	At least 51 years old	59.00				
Differentiated Instruction	21-30 years old	39.65	3.748	0.984	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 years old	39.74				
	41-50 years old	45.75				
	At least 51 years old	59.00				
Direct Instruction	21-30 years old	40.02	4.910	0.295	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 years old	37.79				
	41-50 years old	51.19				
	At least 51 years old	58.17				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	21-30 years old	41.33	4.125	0.248	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 years old	39.71				
	41-50 years old	34.75				
	At least 51 years old	65.67				
Competency-based Learning	21-30 years old	43.73	2.492	0.477	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 years old	36.12				
	41-50 years old	40.69				
	At least 51 years old	51.67				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 15 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison of the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Age Groups. As to Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.505 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Age Groups. On Differentiated Instruction, the p-value was 0.984 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Age Groups. In terms of Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.295 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents’ assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of

Quezon according to Age Groups. Along with Peer Teaching or Tutoring, the p-value was 0.248 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Age Groups. According to Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.477 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Age Groups.

This posted a not significant result since no matter what the age of the teacher, it does not affect the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes. Meaning, no matter the age the result or outcome will be the same.

Suciu and Mata's (2011) study aimed to provide a holistic view of pedagogical approaches closely related with the current approaches in the field of professional competence for the teaching career. Their study covered three dimensions from the perspective of pedagogical approach which include definitions, taxonomy, and holistic view of pedagogical competences for the teacher's teaching career.

Table 16. *Mann Whitney U-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to Civil Status*

Indicators	Civil Status	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	Married	43.61	713.00	0.308	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Single/Separated	38.33				
Differentiated Instruction	Married	44.54	675.00	0.168	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Single/Separated	37.38				
Direct Instruction	Married	42.79	746.50	0.476	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Single/Separated	39.16				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	Married	43.54	716.00	0.316	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Single/Separated	38.40				
Competency-based Learning	Married	40.09	782.50	0.719	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Single/Separated	41.94				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject H

Table 16 shows the Mann Whitney U-Test of the comparison of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status. On Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.308 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status. As to Differentiated Instruction, the p-value was 0.168 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status. According to Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.476 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status. When it comes to Peer Teaching or Tutoring, the p-value was 0.316 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status. In terms of Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.719 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Civil Status.

The findings revealed a not significant result since no matter the marital status is- be it married or single, it has no impact to the quality of pedagogic strategies, or the other way around, the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes is not effective when the basis is the civil status.

Rahman's (2014) study aimed to determine the positive relationship between professional and pedagogical competences based on the performance of Junior High School science teachers in Ternate. The results concluded that professional and pedagogical competences were positively related with the performance of Junior High School science teachers. With the findings, it was stressed that the efforts were done to improve these competencies including educating and training on a regular basis, activating the teachers' activities, preparing science textbooks, continuing education, optimizing supervision, training in the use of various science teaching strategies, using laboratory science training tools, training of IT-based media design, and conducting action research.

Table 17 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment. Along with Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.883 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment. As Differentiated

Instruction, the p-value was 0.507 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment. According to Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.539 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment.

Table 17. *Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to Educational Attainment*

Indicators	Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	H-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	Has Bachelor's Degree	39.58	0.250	0.883	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	With Master's Units	41.44				
	At least has Master's Degree	43.14				
Differentiated Instruction	Has Bachelor's Degree	37.34	1.357	0.507	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	With Master's Units	43.93				
	At least has Master's Degree	42.04				
Direct Instruction	Has Bachelor's Degree	40.22	1.237	0.539	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	With Master's Units	43.76				
	At least has Master's Degree	35.89				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	Has Bachelor's Degree	41.61	0.040	0.980	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	With Master's Units	40.71				
	At least has Master's Degree	40.32				
Competency-based Learning	Has Bachelor's Degree	41.22	0.008	0.996	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	With Master's Units	40.73				
	At least has Master's Degree	41.18				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Also, no matter what education has attained by the teacher, the outcome, or the fruits of the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes is still the same. Educational attainment has no influence on the pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes.

In terms of Peer Teaching or Tutoring, the p-value was 0.980 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment. When it comes to Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.996 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to Educational Attainment.

The study conducted by Carril, Sanmamed & Selles (2013) was focused on identifying and systematizing faculty's roles in virtual environments. It was found out that the pedagogical competences of the teaching staff had higher levels of proficiency which include draft, develop, and execute course contents; organize and promote different tutorial methods; draft, develop and execute learning activities; and organize and facilitate student participation. All these falls under the teaching strategies as pedagogical competences.

Table 18 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank. As to Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.064 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank.

According to Differentiated Instruction, the p-value was 0.067 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank. When it comes to Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.209 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank. In terms of Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.113 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. There is no significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank.

Even what rank the teacher pursued or is promoted, it has the same application of the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching

multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. It means that the rank has no bearing to the use of pedagogic strategies in multigrade settings.

Table 18. *Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to the Teacher's Rank*

Indicators	Teacher's Rank	Mean Rank	H-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	Teacher I	38.26	5.500	0.064	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	40.29				
	At least Teacher III	56.23				
Differentiated Instruction	Teacher I	37.50	5.401	0.067	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	54.08				
	At least Teacher III	45.18				
Direct Instruction	Teacher I	39.16	3.126	0.209	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	39.46				
	At least Teacher III	52.36				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	Teacher I	37.97	9.288	0.010	Reject Ho	Significant
	Teacher II	37.58				
	At least Teacher III	60.68				
Competency-based Learning	Teacher I	39.28	4.353	0.113	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	37.04				
	At least Teacher III	54.41				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

On the other hand, when it comes to Peer Teaching & Tutoring, the p-value was 0.010 which is smaller than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is a significant difference in the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Rank. This denoted that the teachers' assessment of the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in terms of peer teaching or tutoring is higher than those of lower ranks.

Syahruddin et al. (2013) conducted a study titled Teachers' Pedagogical Competence in School-Based Management: A Case Study in a Public Secondary School at Pare-Pare, Indonesia where the extent of the function of teachers' pedagogical competence on the practice of school-based management was investigated. It was inferred that the teachers' pedagogical competence has not been delineated as it was expected. It found out that teachers' creativity was limited by the domination of the government's interference. It was suggested that to improve the quality of school-based management, teachers' continuing professional development was highly required.

Table 19. *Kruskal-Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Pedagogic Strategies in Teaching Multigrade Classes According to the Teacher's Length of Service*

Indicators	Length of Service	Mean Rank	H-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Jump-Jump Strategy	1 to 5 years	36.06	3.314	0.191	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	43.25				
	More than 10 years	49.04				
Differentiated Instruction	1 to 5 years	37.43	4.084	0.130	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	40.38				
	More than 10 years	53.17				
Direct Instruction	1 to 5 years	38.16	2.154	0.341	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	40.96				
	More than 10 years	49.42				
Peer Teaching or Tutoring	1 to 5 years	38.54	0.759	0.684	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	42.38				
	More than 10 years	44.25				
Competency-based Learning	1 to 5 years	41.57	0.496	0.781	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	39.19				
	More than 10 years	44.46				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 19 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison of the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service.

On Jump-Jump Strategy, the p-value was 0.191 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service. As to Differentiated Instruction, the p-value was 0.130 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference on the

respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service. In terms of Direct Instruction, the p-value was 0.341 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service. As regards Peer Teaching or Tutoring, the p-value was 0.684 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service. When it comes to Competency-based Learning, the p-value was 0.781 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to the Teacher's Length of Service.

The longevity of teacher's service to the school has no effect on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes. No matter how long or how short a teacher serves the school does not completely affect the pedagogic strategies in multigrade instruction.

Pedagogic knowledge was regarded as knowledge about the hypothetical forms of these modalities, the conditions under which they may apply and the consequences they may have. While this abstract conception of pedagogy as system was helpful in thinking about and classifying different pedagogies, it leaves open the question of teacher agency and its function in mediating between the needs of school and the state on the one hand, and the needs of learners on the other. Multigrade teachers may have different degrees of control over what is learned in their classrooms and how, nevertheless, their capability to come to be informed and principled decisions about pedagogic practices is of vital importance. Edwards (2021) defined pedagogy as an act involving those who were teaching in informed principles of learners, knowledge, and environments to control the environments in ways that help learners apply their knowledge available to them. It is an intense, complex, and discursive act, which requires considerable expertise. The ability of teachers to rationalize their decisions is also an important part of pedagogy. Pedagogy is the act of teaching together with its dispersed discourse. It is what one needs to know, and the skills one needs to command, to make and rationalize the many different kinds of decisions of which teaching is applied. (Alexander, 2014, p. 11).

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived, the following were concluded:

Most of the respondents were aged between 21 and 30 years old, predominantly female, married, possessed Master's Units, held the Teacher I position, and had been serving the school for a period ranging from 1 to 5 years.

The quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes was given a very good rating in the Division of Quezon. When it comes to Peer Teaching or Tutoring, it showed that the administrators and teachers apply differentiated learning instruction to ensure learning will take place in school. According to Competency-based Learning, it stated that competency-based education is applied by the Multigrade teachers following the K-12 Curriculum and MELCs based competencies. In terms of Direct Instruction, it elicited that multigrade Instruction is evaluated or assessed through formative and summative assessments for the period.

The respondents often encountered problems in using pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon. This showed that the students lack gadgets to be used for internet classes for differentiated learning approach. Next item elicited that there are problems with the internet connectivity for differentiated approach. This was followed by the statement which said that the location of Multigrade schools is the reason why facilities and other construction are not readily available.

There is no significant difference on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to profile except for Teacher's Rank on Peer Teaching or Tutoring which is statistically significant on the respondents' assessments on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to profile.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were recommended:

Pursue Graduate Schooling for Continuing Professional Development for the teachers in the school, for promotion, for commitment and for career development through conducts of action research, attending seminars and trainings, and enrolling to Master's or Doctorate Degree programs.

Conduct lectures for Multigrade Instruction to supplement or to supplicate the needs of the learners through parental conference and online learning instruction to learners.

Supply gadgets for the learners to be used for internet classes for differentiated learning approach either through MOOE or PTA funds to be given to the learners so that they can conduct Online Learning Instruction.

Since there are no significant differences on the quality of pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes in the Division of Quezon according to profile, it is recommended to disseminate information about pedagogic strategies in teaching multigrade classes except for Teacher's Rank under Peer Teaching or Tutoring where it is recommended to strengthen Peer Teaching or Tutoring so that both

Teachers and Students will benefit from the pedagogic strategy being used. This can be achieved through assigning a committee or coordinators in the school so that learners monitor and supervise, including their multigrade teachers.

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